

and (III) exhibited a strong band at 1710 cm^{-1} for an isolated carbonyl group. It is a general observation in these reactions that the 3-oxo group is preferably more reactive than the 6-oxo groups⁶. Therefore the strong band at 1710 cm^{-1} is assigned

to $-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}6-$ in compounds (II) and (III). The configuration at spirane carbon at C3 in compounds (II) and (III) was determined by ^1H nmr values. It has been found that in the case of isomer containing axial $\text{C}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{N}}$ bond, ring methylene protons

($-\text{S}-\underset{\text{Spirane}}{\text{CH}_2}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-$) signal is shifted downfield by $\delta 0.04-0.10$ ppm as compared to methylene protons signal where $\text{C}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{N}}$ bond is equatorial⁷. Com-

parison of the ^1H nmr values for ring methylene protons in compounds (II) and (III) confirmed that C3- $\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{N}}$ bond is axial in (II) and equatorial in (III).

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Girinimbine and Koenimbine from *Murraya exotica* Linn.

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IN continuation of the investigation on *Murraya exotica* Linn. in our laboratory, from which coumarins¹⁻⁵, carbazoles⁶, flavonoids^{7,8} were reported, we now report two carbazoles, koenimbine (I) $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}$ and girinimbine (II) $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}$ from the same plant.

(I)

(II)

The alkaloids were obtained from the neutral fraction of the petroleum ether ($60-80^\circ$) extract of the stem bark of *M. exotica* on chromatography over alumina and characterised by ir and uv spectral data and also by direct comparison with authentic samples.

Though the yield of the first carbazole (I) is very low, the isolation and identification of koenimbine and girinimbine from *M. exotica* Linn. (a member of the genus *Murraya*) is important from taxonomic standpoint.

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Phenyl Hydrazine-N-Dithiocarbamate : A New Gravimetric Reagent for the Determination and Separation of Copper(II) and Nickel(II)

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ALTHOUGH a lot of work has been carried out on dithiocarbamates and on their analytical¹⁻⁷ applications, phenyl hydrazine-N-dithiocarbamate has not been used in analytical field. Phenyl hydrazine-N-dithiocarbamate has been employed as a new gravimetric reagent for the separation and

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